
A CHRONOLOGICAL VIEW OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL THEORIES OF ADMINISTRATION AND MANAGEMENT VIS-A-VIS NIGERIA'S ORGANIZATIONAL EVOLUTION

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Abstract

This paper discusses the development of organizational theory by going back in time to identify some of the issues that led to the development of specific theories of organization and their proponents. The study also, gives a brief but concise discussion on the importance of organizational theories while stating their key properties. Similarly, this work highlights the evolution of Nigeria's public and private organizations by identifying their theoretical basis. The study deployed descriptive approach while relying on secondary data as its tool of analysis. Findings reveal that organizational theories have always been integral to solving administration and management challenges in public and private organizations. The paper noted the importance of culture and leadership in addressing the ever-changing features of society. The research concludes that the problems of corruption at the leadership level undermine the adoption and implementation of some of the organizational theories discussed in Nigeria. It however, recommended that fighting corruption and developing homegrown and culturally adaptive theories that are capable of solving peculiar local challenges will aid the survival, growth and development of resilient organizations and mitigate the problems identified as bedeviling organizational development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Organization, Organizational theory, Theory

Introduction

The evolution of organizational theory can be traced to the emergence of organizations that were created to transform discoveries in science, arts, manufacturing, business and entrepreneurship to purchaseable goods and services. The idea was to develop effective and efficient ways of managing emerging business concerns in a cost effective manner using the instrumentality of opportunities presented by social changes and economic conditions of human and material resources to address the challenges that confronted human's endeavour in harnessing resources for profitable venture (Adegboye, 2013).

Going back to thousands of years, managers have always grappled with the challenges that today's managers confront. As early as 1100 B.C, the Chinese practiced the four management functions of planning, organizing, leading, and controlling. The Greeks had between 400 B.C and 350 B.C, recognized management as separate art that must be systematically and scientifically studied as an approach. The Romans on their part deployed decentralization as a veritable tool to manage their vast empire, even before the birth of Christ. The medieval times saw the venations standardizing production through the use of assembly lines, the warehousing of raw materials and finished goods and the use of inventory systems to keep track of inward and outward movement of goods (Okolie and Oyise, 2021).

In spite of all of these attempts, most management practices were done on 'trial and error' basis until the challenges of industrial revolution change everything. The volatility of that era required that management be treated as a formal discipline that needed academic inputs to mitigate the existential threats that confronted businesses (Edo-Osagie and Ebeh, 2023).

Therefore, starting from the industrial revolution era the discipline of management and the development of organizational theories grew phenomenally. Organizational theory is crucial to understanding the philosophical underpins responsible for why organisations act the way they do (Odor, 2018). The organizational theory that drives the workings of any corporate entity tells much about the relationship of such organization with its publics (within and without). It is on the basis of this that it is important to familiarize ourselves with the various organizational theories that have been postulated to describe, organize, explain and streamline organizations in their drive to attain maximum benefits in pursuing the goals that they set for themselves.

It must be stated without equivocation that the organizational workspace and its surrounding environment have changed over the years, though the objectives of setting up organizations remain the same, i.e profit making and profit maximization, hence the deployment of technology and information management in the management and administration of businesses. In the 21st Century, technology has deepened the realities of managing organizations. And it is in the light of this, that Amodu and Ologbosere (2021) argue in support of the importance of information management to organizational success. They contend that the realities of the VUCA* world has globally make organizations to continuously experience accelerated changes and development. What it then means, as Amodu and Ologbosere (2021) continue to argue, is that understanding the correlations between technology and information management using the VUCA and the DIKAR** models and appropriately deploying them would lead to appropriate actions or decisions especially if such actions are founded on knowledge. They contending that such knowledge must be founded on information derived from data.

The key individuals that influenced the study of organizations, and their contributions to the development of organizational and management theories include: Mary Parker Follett (1868–1973) for her pioneering work in organizational behaviour, Chester Barnard (1886–1961) for his contributions to organizational theory and management and Herbert Simon (1916–2001) for his influential inputs on organizational theory (Okolie and Oyise, 2021).

Definition of Terms

Theory

It can be defined as a systematic and formalized expression of ideas, principles and concepts that explains and predicts phenomena, behaviours, or events within a specific domain or field of study. Its characteristics include: systematic presentation (i.e. organized, structured), abstraction (mental extrapolation), explanatory (to make clear and understandable), predictive (project future event or behavior), testable (tested and validated through research and experimentation), generalization (can be applied across broad spectrum of situations and contexts) and, coherence (logical and consistent in its framework).

There are various types of theory, examples of which include; descriptive, explanatory, predictive, prescriptive and normative theories. The basic functions of theory are to explain, predict, analysis, synthesize and guide users (Easterly-Smith, 2021).

Organization

This is a structured system of individuals, groups, and processes designed to achieve specific goals, objectives, and purposes. The attributes of organization are; structure (roles, responsibilities and relationships), goals (objectives and purpose), processes (procedures and workflows), people (individuals and teams), resources (physical, financial, technological infrastructure), communication (information flow and exchange), coordination (integration of activities and tasks), and adaptability (ability to respond to change (Robbins, 2020).

Organizational theory

Following from the definitions given above, organizational theory can be said to be the study of organization using systematic and formalized expression of ideas, principles and concepts to explain, describe, organize and predict the behaviours, processes, structure and goals of organization.

Stages of Organizational Theory Development

In terms of the overview of the development of organizational theory and some of the characteristics of the theories, the work of Okolie and Oyise (2021) would be used as the basis of our discussion. The following stages are gleaned for the purpose of this write-up:

Classical Period (1900 – 1940)

- (i) **Scientific Management Theory:** This is the era when Frederick Taylor (1911) emphasized the development of production systems that allows for efficiency, standardization and specialization. The theory emphasizes the capacity to make man behave as machine through routinization of tasks.
- (ii) **Administrative Theory:** The major proponent of this theory is Henri Fayol (1916). Fayol in his drive to better the administration of organisations identified 14 principles that should be deployed to manage them. These principles are: (i) Division of work, (ii) Authority, (iii) Discipline, (iv) Unity of command, (v) Unity of direction, (vi) Subordination of individual interest, (vii) Remuneration, (viii)

Centralization, (ix) Scalar chain, (x) Order, (xi) Equity, (xii) Stability of tenure, (xiii) Initiative, and (xiv) Espirit de Corps.

- (iii) **Bureaucratic Theory:** This theory is attributed to Max Weber (1922). The theory focuses on workplace arrangement that is based on hierarchy, rules and impersonal relationships. The objective is to create a system that is not haphazard in its operations. His focus is to eliminate personal vagaries and individuals' influences on the workings of an organization right from the point of recruitment to the point of retirement/disengagement.

Human Relations Period (1940 – 1960)

- (i) **Hawthorne Studies:** This study is carried out by Elton Mayo (1930). In this study it was revealed that social factors as family life, acceptability, respect and wellbeing play very significant role in the productivity of employees. Similarly, the study hammered on the significance of employee motivation in organizational productivity. The key social needs he identified was categorized into two broad headings. The first one is what he termed as the primary social needs comprising of security of job and stability; sense of belongingness and affiliation, recognition, acknowledgement appreciation; and participation through involvement in decision-making. The second is secondary needs which include social interaction like friendship; status recognition like prestige and respect; conducive atmosphere for personal growth and development; and autonomy which allows for independence and self-direction.
- (ii) **Human Resource Approach:** This approach is credited to David McClelland (1955). The crux of the approach is centred on paying attention to employee needs while also emphasizing the importance of motivation to organizational progress. The theory otherwise known as 'Acquired Needs Theory's identified three primary employee needs. These needs were:
- Need for Achievement (nAch): Success, achievement, accomplishment.
 - Need for Affiliation (nAff): Social relationship, belongingness, collaboration.
 - Need for Power (nPow): Control, influence and authority. Embedded within the concept of nAch is the idea of setting challenging goals, seeking feedback and taking calculated risk; for nAff is valuing teamwork, seeking social interaction and avoiding conflict; while nPow is geared towards seeking influence, enjoying leadership roles and sometimes prioritizing personal gains
- (iii) **Participative Management:** This theory is postulated by Chris Argyris (1957). The centerpiece of the theory is based on the significance of putting in place within the organization a system or process that allows or encourages employee involvement in the management of the organization. The importance of this approach is that employees who are involved in decision-making tend to accept these decisions and are much willing to carry out the decisions to their logical ends since they view themselves as part of decision making process.

Contingency Period (1960 – 1980)

- (i) **Contingency Theory:** This theory emanated from Joan Woodward (1965). Woodward identified the importance of technology in the structure of

organization. The theory also, highlighted the need to pay attention to environmental factors in the management of an organization (Dikert, Paasivaara, Lessenius, 2018).

- (ii) **Systems Theory:** Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968) postulated the significance of addressing the functionality of organization on the viability of the various parts that make-up an organization. For him, no organization can be said to be working optimally if any of its part is not functioning to capacity. The inefficiency in one part would have negative ramifications on the overall output of the organization. Therefore, for an organization to be deemed productive every department must be fully functional.
- (iii) **Organisational Development:** The theory is attributed to Warren Bennis (1969). The theory is focused on organizational change and growth. It views organization as a system (i.e. interconnected, dynamic and adaptive), that allows for collaborative leadership (shared power, empowerment and participation) with focus on human resources (skills development, motivation and commitment) without jeopardizing process (communication, collaboration and problem-solving), by deploying data-driven decision-making capabilities through research and feedback so as to arrive at informed decisions.

Modern Period (1980 – 2000).

- (i) **Chaos Theory:** The proponent of this theory is Ilya Prigogine (1980). The concern of the theory is majorly to see the management of organisations from the point of complexity and adaptability. The theory highlighted complexity and non-linearity as basis to understanding organizational behaviour. It views organization as a complex, dynamic system, stating that non-linearity can lead to significant unpredictable effects even from small changes. Likewise, the theory sees organisations as self-organising, that is, an entity that can reorganize themselves and adapt to new challenges without external intervention or direction. When this happens it can lead to the emergence of new patterns and structures due to interaction, this can allow organizations to maintain stability from energy exchange.
- (ii) **Total Quality Management:** This theory is credited to W. Edwards Deming (1986). The emphasis is to put in place measures that would ensure the continuous improvement of organisations. The theory while highlighting organization's improvement, equally promotes customer satisfaction. Deming outline 14 points that are crucial to organizational success, these are; (i) constancy of purpose (stable long-term goals) (ii) adopting philosophy that emphasis quality and continuous improvement (iii) stop dependence on supervision/inspection instead build quality into process (iv) harmonise supplier by fostering partnerships (v) improve constantly by encouraging continuous learning (vi) institute training through skills development and knowledge seeking (vii) institute leadership by replacing supervision with leadership, (viii) eliminate fear by encouraging open communication (ix) break down barriers by fostering teamwork and encouraging collaborative action (x) do away with sloganeering and rhetorics, rather focus on action (xi) deemphasize quotas and quantity, instead promote quality (xii) eliminate barrier that forbid workers from being owners of the organization (xiii) institute programmes that would encourage self-improvement, and (xiv) encourage all employees to get involve in accomplishing the transformative objectives of organizations.

Contemporary Period (2000 – Date)

- (i) **Network Organisation Theory:** This theory emphasizes organizational practices that recognize interconnectedness and networking in organizations. This theory is propounded by Nitin Nohria (1992). It sees organizations as webs of relationships that works on interdependence through units interconnectedness thereby leading to fluid boundaries between units. This allows organizations to create network adaption and evolution through interactions leading to the emergence of new patterns and structures. The theory emphasizes decentralized decision-making, flexibility and adaptability, collaboration and cooperation, knowledge-sharing and creation, and flat/horizontal structure. Its benefits include; increased innovation and adaptability, better communication and collaboration, greater flexibility and responsiveness leading to better alignment with changing environments.
- (ii) **Knowledge Management Approach:** This approach emanated from Ikujiro Nonaka (1995). For him, for organizations to thrive there must be deliberate drive towards knowledge creation and sharing, emphasizing knowledge utilization to drive organizational innovation and competitiveness. The theory calls for the recognition and deployment of tacit knowledge (personal experiential knowledge), explicit knowledge (documented, codified knowledge), shared context for knowledge creation, and knowledge conversion as keys to organizational productivity.
- (iii) **Complexity Theory:** This theory finds expression in the work of Ralph Stacey (1996). The focus of the theory is the need for management to explore organizational complexity and uncertainty. This theory also recognizes factors as complexity, uncertainty, non-linearity, self-reinvention and emergence of new patterns and structures from the interactions that go on in organizations as crucial for survival. This theory aligns with modern organizational theory that preaches innovation and adaptability that are commonly reflective of the complex nature of the globalized business environment, bringing to the fore the readiness of organization to strategically manage these complexities.
- (iv) **Agile Organization Theory:** Jeff Sutherland (2014) postulates that any organization that seeks to achieve its set objectives must emphasize flexibility and adaptability. For him, the organization at minimal cost and within a reasonable time frame must be able to align itself to the changes that occur within the industry and achieve stability in meeting its obligation both within and without. It highlights the ability to respond quickly to change, break down work into smaller, manageable tasks, empower teams to make decisions while inculcating structured approach to respond on project management. Similarly, the theory prioritises individuals' interactions over processes and tools, software over comprehensive documentation, customer collaboration over contract negotiation, and responding to change over following a plan.

Nigeria's Organizational Evolution: Pre-Colonial to Contemporary Era:

A proper understanding of the evolution of Nigeria's organizational development requires looking at every strand of Nigeria's drive towards organizational success by going back to its formative beginnings and moving towards the present (Ivongbe, et al. 2021; Edo-Osagie and Ebeh, 2023). In doing this, this can be discussed under six (6) broad sub-headings, which are:

- i. Pre-Colonial era (Before 1800s)**

This era witnessed the existence of traditional organizations of tribes, kingdoms, and empires. This stage was essentially driven by informal economic engagement in areas of trade, agriculture, and craftsmanship.
- ii. Colonial Era (1800s – 1960)**

This stage was noted for the establishment of bureaucratic structures and institutions like the Nigerian Civil Service, the creation of missionary organizations, the introduction of western education, and healthcare service systems. The period also saw the growth of private sector companies like the United Africa Company (UAC) and John Holt.
- iii. Post-Colonial Era (1960 – 1980)**

This stage of organizational development in Nigeria witnessed the nationalization of key sectors of the economy (oil, banking). Similarly, there was the establishment of government owned companies like the Nigeria National Petroleum Corporation (NNPC). The era also led to the promotion of indigenization policy where local ownership and control of hitherto foreign owned businesses were championed through national legislations.
- iv. Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) Era (1980 – 1990)**

This is the era of economic liberalization leading to privatization, deregulation, and trade liberalization. This period also saw implementation of organizational restructuring that led to adoption of modern management practices in both private and public companies (Adeyeye, 2015, Oyedele, 2019).
- v. Democratization Era (1990 – 2020)**

This period marked the era of increased private sector growth in areas that were hitherto viewed as exclusively government business areas like telecommunications, petroleum refining, and electricity generation and distribution. These developments led to the emergence of companies like MTN, Glo, Dangote Refinery and Gencos and Discos who have become major players in these sectors. Similarly, privately owned banks with huge capital outlay started playing critical roles in global businesses and infrastructural financing. This era also saw the establishment of specialized government economic and financial monitoring agencies with prosecutory powers like the Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC), Nigeria Extractive Industry Transparency Initiative (NEITI), and Independent Corrupt Practices Commission (ICPC). The civil society organisations (CSOs) influence also grew exponentially during this period.
- vi. Contemporary Era (2010 – present).**

This stage is witnessing the growth of digital economy with the expanding growth of tech startups and e-commerce platforms. It is also leading to public-private partnership (PPP) collaborations between government and private sector. This era is encouraging organizational innovation by adopting agile methodologies and innovation hubs (Adeyeye, 2017).

Organisational theory has impacted Nigerian organizations in myriads of positive ways, influencing their structure, processes and overall effectiveness (Kappe, 2010; Masoje, 2018; Oyedele, 2019). Some of these positive impacts are briefly discussed below:

- (i) **Management practices enhancement:** The adoption of modern organizational theories like contingency theory, agile organization theory greatly improved decision-making and problem-solving outcomes in organisations like Nigerian Breweries PLC (TQM), GTB (Agile), Dangote (Contingency).
- (ii) **Increase productivity:** The implementation of efficient organizational structure like bureaucracy and matrix has led to boost in productivity and efficiency.
- (iii) **Improved decision-making capacity:** The deployment of decision-making models like the rational decision-making theory leads to more informed decisions within organizations.
- (iv) **Gives room for innovation:** Theories like organizational learning and knowledge management have encouraged creativity, ingenuity and innovation in Nigerian organisations like First Bank PLC (Learning), and MTN (Knowledge).
- (v) **Quality leadership:** The adoption of leadership theories like transformational leadership has immensely improves leadership effectiveness in Nigerian organisations (Akinwunmi, 2020).

Conclusion

Consequent on the concise discourse of the chronological development of organizational theory, organizational theories and models, and the evolution of Nigeria's organizational development, it is important to note that in the specific case of Nigeria and other developing nations factors as cultural constraints (Adegboye, 2013), limited resources, corruption, resistance to change, leadership failure and lack of expertise (Masoje, 2018) have continued to stifle some of the gains that could have accrued from adopting and implementing these organizational theories. For instance, in the management of government and private organizations in Nigeria, Amodu (2021), highlighted the importance of a good leader. This is important because a good leader is expected to think through situations and articulate processes or mechanisms for engendering development. He, however, opined [sadly though] that ...one recurring theme that has become synonymous with leadership in Nigeria is corruption. This situation portends a very grave danger to the present and future management of government and private business organizations in the country.

Recommendation

Having traced development of organizational theories, their proponents and the important roles they play in the administration and management of public and private organizations in the world in generally and specifically in Nigeria, it is therefore recommended that the following steps should be taken if Nigeria is to benefit more from the deployment of these theories.

- It is important that efforts should be made to develop context-specific organizational theories for Nigerian organizations. This is significant so as to address issues of administration and management that are peculiar to the Nigerian situation.
- Encourage increased management education and training. Efforts should be made to educationally empower Nigerian personnel by allowing greater access to specialized administration and management schools through sponsorship and reduced tuition fees.
- Stimulate innovation and entrepreneurship skills acquisition programmes. There should be continuous in-service training, workshops, seminars programmes for all categories of staff so as to keep them updated about the changing nature of administration and

management practices. This would accentuate a culture of continuous learning and improvement for the betterment of the society.

- Tackle the challenge of corruption. Corruption should be fought with renewed vigour by all and sundry. Government and its agencies especially anti-corruption bodies must be alive to their responsibility by quashing unwholesome organizational practices while encouraging and recognizing ethical leadership practices (Adeyeye, 2017, Oyedele, 2017) so as to let Nigerian organizations to fully harness the benefits of adopting and implementing some of the organizational theories so far discussed.

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Endnotes

*VUCA, acronym for volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity (Werren and Burt, 1985). See Amodu and Ologbosere, (2021). Critical overview of management, DIKAR model and technology in 21st Century for further reading.

**DIKAR, acronym for data, information, knowledge, action, and result (Venkatra, M., 1991). See Amodu and Ologbosere, (2021). Critical overview of management, DIKAR model and technology in 21st Century for further reading.

°For further reading see Dikert, Paasivaara and Lessenius, (2018). Agile organizational transformation: A case study. *Journal of Systems and Software*, 111.